

Swami Vivekanand – Works and Ideas

Dr. Vishakha Singh

Assistant Professor

Department of Political Science

Dayanand Girls P. G. College, Kanpur

Narendranath Dutt who was well known as Swami Vivekanand was a splendid personality. Vivekanand had a kind heart and he was always concerned to the society. He was given the status of a Radical, patriot prophet of modern India. He represented India all over the world. The people of America were very much impressed when he spoken about the religious prosperity of India. His thought was coming all over the world and all religions in one thread. Vivekanand was a spiritual person and he wanted to promote spirituality in all over the world.

Early life

On 12th January, 1863, Swami Vivekanand was born into a prosperous family. His mother Bhuvnesh vary devi was a religious woman, she was highly pious spiritual lady. Mother's education Convert Vivekanand into a spiritual and curious person, who was concerned about the welfare of society. His mother made him disciplined and self-controlled person. His father Vishwanath was an attorney at law.

His father was scholar of English and literature. He had a progressive vision about the life and concerned for the welfare of society and human being. He was kind hearted and always supported poor people. In this way Narendranath was impressed by the inspiration and guidelines of his father and mother's values. He had too much respect for his mother and said that, **“I am indebted to my mother for whatever Knowledge I have acquired”**.

Narendranath was very much bright student in his school life. His teachers and classmates also recognized his brilliance. While growing up Vivekanand concerned about the society and its problems unemployment, poverty etc. He was very much active in social programs and meetings. In 1879, he joined the Presidency College of Calcutta for the further higher education.

Vivekanand came to know about **Ram Krishna Paramhans** by the lecture of his professor Hastie. He spoke about the religious and moral values of human beings. His lecture on the poem of Wordsworth, ‘The excursion’ influenced him very much. The excursion by William Wordsworth is a contemplative exportation of the profound impact of industrialization during the romantic era. Industrialization and urbanization are symbol to progress but it had ruined the environmental and natural beauty.

Spiritual thirst

Now he was devotee of Ramkrishna Paramhans and accepted him his Guru. The teachings and education given by Swami Ramkrishna Paramhans enlightened whole life of swami Vivekanand. After the death of his

Guru Swami ji taken renunciation and wandered all over world for the circulation of ideas and principals of Ramkrishna Mission. While wandering India Vivekanand had great experience of the poverty and miserable condition of India. He was very much eager to vanish this potable condition.

His environment and its influences on Vivekanand

Swami Vivekanand was very much brilliant. He had a great knowledge of all subjects. He was very much influenced by the scientific atmosphere of his time. He read. J.S. mill, French philosophers, Kent, Comet, Spenser and Hegel etc.

The reformist movement of India as Arya Samaj Movement, Brahma Samaj Movement inspired him for the service of mankind. By the study of western political thinkers and movements he came to know about democracy, equality and importance of rights. He knew that for whole development of the nation and society liberty, rights are necessary for people of India. These movements and atmosphere inspired him for making a new path for human being but he was not fully satisfied by the goals, principals and achievements of these societies. He ultimately wanted the goal of human life, meaning of human life. His curiosity and willingness were satisfied when he met Swami Ramkrishna Paramhans. He was the answer of his every question and end of his eager and curious mind.

His mentor settled down his aggressive faith in logic and made him understand the value of personal realization than of intellectual conviction. In short, the environment and atmosphere of 19th century Bengal and Hindu Vedant developed Swami Vivekanand's ideas and thoughts. In his view point man and God have no difference, they are united.

During his tour from Himalayas to Cape Comorin, he gained experiences about socioeconomic and religious conditions of his countrymen. He Knew the key factors of social backwardness of India. He was very much worried about the down fall of Indian society, moral decline and orthodoxy of religion. He admitted that right of cast and religion are mainly responsible for the backwardness of society. Vivekanand had the view that dogmatism in any realm is the surest opponent of growth and development.

Idea of Self

Idea of self is related to inner consciousness and different to bodily activities. In thought of Swami Vivekanand spirituality holds twin goals that of realization of one's own self and to land to attain a similar goal of other humans. This realization can make people divine, pure, sensitive and just. If anyone can realize himself and his inner soul he can understand humans in proper way. Vedant philosophy is the base of universal love. The understanding of Vedant leads to development of love for all.

Self is related to 'Atmananda' of as Taittiriya Upanishad says happiness or Anand is reflection of the happiness of self. According to Vivekanand happiness of inner soul is very much significant for the inner and outer development of human being but Vivekanand's happiness consists of Individual freedom in his view.

Individual freedom does not relate to isolation but is deeply related to the welfare of society. This concept is necessary of the perfection of society because freedom and liberty make perfect people and they can make perfect society. The perfect society means there will be harmony between people and they will be devoted to each other. There will be good balance between Spiritualism and materialism. This way humans will acquire a highly satisfied and balanced life.

Concept of Nar and Narayana

Swami ji gave the idea of Nar and Narayana which was one of his famous ideas. In his thought Nar is considered human and Narayan are symbol of divine power or deity. In Hindu mythology Nar Narayana were two brothers spiritually related to lord Vishnu. They established many services for the welfare of society. Another story of Nar Narayan was related to the epic of Mahabharat where Nar is Arjun and Narayan is Shri Krishna. Lord Vishnu was symbol of dharma. He came for the preservation of the whole world. Nar and Narayana had come to vanish the sin and miseries of mankind.

In the view of Swami Ji, the concept of Nar and Narayan is symbol of service of whole world. According to Vivekanand There is no major difference between God and Human being. God is only superior form of man. His Guru Paramhans taught him for the service of deprived class of society. There is no difference between God-Service and Human-service. Swami Vivekanand envisioned this phrase Nar Narayan as "Service to humanity is service to God". In man's heart God resides. This concept made the philosophy of Vivekanand's life. According to Vivekanand one's self is related to universal self, realization of our inner self is realization of universal world. He wanted to emphasize people to look for God in every individual. He was not in favour of ritualistic practices, but in spite of this view he wanted to serve the people in miserable conditions. Instead of paraphernalia of worship he wanted to serve the poor Daridra Narayana.

Vivekanand is very popular in young ones his birthday is celebrated **Yuva Divas** in India. Even after a lapse of half of century, people still obey his principles.

Teaching of Gautama Buddha was also greatly influenced Swami Vivekananda, as his Main Concern was alleviating the suffering of mankind and finding the way to overcome the miseries of people Swami Vivekananda lauded the ethical activism of Gautam Buddha as he renounced worldly life and even did not believe in Personal God or a personal soul. He mainly focused on good for all throughout his life.

Swami Vivekanand tried the enriched the life of man with message of Vedanta and uplift his moral life without being any believe in Religion and God. According to Swami Vivekananda Advaita Vedanta preach the message of Universal love and renunciation rejecting the nation of Superior or Inferior. He also believed that no nation can attain prosperity and strength without the strength and good character of citizens and Vedanta can enable the citizens to attend strength and good character.